

FOREIGN MODELS OF MANAGEMENT.

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Foreign models of management. There are three main models of management. They are all very different from each other, they have their strengths and weaknesses. Marketing, Japan and the American model of governance: At the moment, these models are popular models. liq. Many of the foreign states had a significant focus on agriculture, industry, trade theory, but also management practices, taking into account their specific characteristics, taking into account its history for all. At the same time, such models of governance, such as the United States and Japan, have been radically reconsidered. Management models include basic management principles, goals and structures, strategic vision, values being developed together, order and their elements, analytical control and monitoring, organizational structure of all interactions, motivation and development driving policy forces. So how important is the management model. Let's start with the US. The control system of companies established in this country is very difficult. The nature of the relationship between all domestic company offices is determined by the type of business, previously established. U.S. firms in the past, the organization was trestovskuyu, so now well-known companies ("Ford Motors", "Chrysler"), enterprises that are part of the production offices, completely deprived of self-sufficiency. Their leaders are subordinate to the heads of the same production offices. American management style has its own characteristics. In this case, the responsibilities of each individual employee are clearly defined. The essence of the American model is that there is a preliminary judgment - the success of the company depends on factors that lie in its territory. This only implies a reduction in the cost of identifying various internal reserves, in terms of rational organization, production, efficiency, use of available resources and increase in productivity.

The U.S. model seeks candidates for relatively specific positions that can be said to be tailored to the system. Japanese governance significantly increases the competitiveness of the national economy. Here we are at the maximum focus on technical and technological innovations. The Japanese model of intelligent features management - it is, first of all, the so-called system of lifelong employment. In addition, the help depends on the ceramic. An important element is the organization of group activities. The ceramics are also paid by, as well as on the basis of their contribution to the process of quality and rationalization. There is a lifelong learning system directly in the workplace. But the marketing model relies on a self-fulfilling human being. In addition, the company is a living organism composed of people united by common values. The company, as well as constant external factors, the main factor is adaptation, renewal - it is consumption.

America is one of the most developed countries in the world. America is a leader in modern, contemporary management styles. The American economy is a free economy and

people live their lives freely without much social scrutiny and barriers. They want to live independently and are accustomed to the "hiring and firing" style of governance. Contract recruitment began in the United States, followed by other countries around the world.

Key features of the American management system:

1. The decision-making process is very fast and it is done on an individual basis. Decisions are made at different levels of government by people working at these levels or by high-level individuals.
2. The system follows a bureaucratic and formal organizational structure with a clear line of personal responsibility and accountability
3. American companies respond to workforce requirements typically by conducting interviews on campus and inviting people to work for other companies.

It is useful in developing a culture of frequent jumping. The pay system for internships is firmly established and widespread in times of sharp inflation, based on the high value placed on experience and skills and the high cost of living for high-cost employees. The vital employment system was established in 191 (1920), when the workers' movement was active to provide and pacify the skilled labor force, in parallel with which unskilled, outsourced contract and temporary workers were hired and skilled workers of the turnkey manufacturing industries were placed from the parent company to its affiliates. This inevitably led to the formation of a dual structure of employment. In the past, even today, technological innovation is changing Japan's management style in various ways. The main focus of education and training in the company is on the transition from newly hired employees to middle and senior employees to ensure their adaptation to new and new technologies. The payroll system for internships has been combined with a payroll system based on a revised job function in the context of rapidly evolving technological innovations. Management concepts and practices are aimed at continuously expanding wealth and growth potential. Technological innovation, however, leads to fewer job opportunities in the manufacturing sector (due to the mechanization of the production process), which reduces the workforce in the office, while also encouraging scheduling expansion.

This is called the development of the "software economy". This has helped reduce direct employment and diversify, increase and reduce working hours for indirect employment. It is therefore difficult to predict in which areas Japan's traditional management style will continue or change. On the plus side, even though the priority of where to work does not disappear altogether, the preference for the profession is growing. requires higher wages than thousands. If necessary, the enterprise converts indirect employment into direct employment, thereby achieving a long-term reduction in wages. This is one aspect of the development of the software economy, the possible outcome of which is the diversity and professionalization of technical professions, which in turn increases social mobility.